

Taxonomic notes on Palaearctic longhorned beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Part. 4

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Abstract. New localities of 5 species are proposed. Not available 10 synonyms of *Pachytodes erraticus* (Dalman, 1817) used as available by Danilevsky (2020) must be regarded as unavailable. An aberrant *Stenurella* (s.str.) *melanura* is shown. *Trichoferus* Wollaston, 1854 = *Trichiformafascius* Özdikmen, 2025a, **syn. nov.** *Bulbocerambyx gui* (Lin, Miroshnikov & He, 2025), **comb. n.**, *B. miaobenfui* (Lin, Miroshnikov & He, 2025), **comb. n.**, *B. liyuani* (Lin, Miroshnikov & He, 2025), **comb. n.** *Obrium cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767) from Russian Far East can be *O. c. shimomurai* Takakuwa, 1984. Özdikmen (2025b) proposed 4 unacceptable modifications in Anaglyptini. *Pogonocherus* (*Trichorondonia* Breuning, 1965 = *Prominensipenna* Özdikmen, 2025c, **syn. nov.**). *Agapanthia* (*Epopetes*) *dahli olegpaki* **ssp. n.** is described from Kazakhstan (Tarbagatai).

Introduction

A series of 3 articles (2024a, 2024b, 2025) with taxonomy remarks on Palaearctic Cerambycidae are followed with 13 new notes.

Results

1. One female of *Brachyta* (s. str.) *interrogationis* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 1) was collected in Southern Kazakhstan: Karatau Ridge (10 km SE Karaoi vill., 43°13'58"N, 70°11'16"E, 700 m, 14.5.2025, O. Pak leg.), is preserved in the collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia). The taxon is preliminary identified here as *B.* (s. str.) *i. duodecimmaculata* (Fabricius, 1781).

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2. Two series of *Brachyta* (s. str.) *interrogationis miroshnikovii* Lazarev, 2011 (Figs 2-3) from Caucasus are preserved in the collection of V.E. Ustinov (Moscow, Russia): 2 males, Russia, Karachay-Cherkessia, Daut, 10.7.1994; 3 males, Russia, Dagestan, Buynaksk District, Verkhny Kazalin, 10.7.2004, V. Sofronov. It is the first record of the taxon for Dagestan.

3. Most of the synonyms of *Pachytodes erraticus* (Dalman, 1817) have been published by M. Pic as variations, but often different variations were published from one locality. All such names are unavailable.

The position of many synonyms needs verification.

erraticus erraticus Dalman, 1817a: 490 (*Leptura*) **E**: AL BH CT CZ GE KZ MC ME PL RO SB SK SL SP ST ?SZ UK **A**: ES KZ WS XIN

heyrovskii Pic, 1924c: 26 (*Leptura*) ["Bohème"]

russicus Pic, 1898h: 54 ["Russie"]

erraticus erythrurus Küster, 1848b: 90 ["Türkei"] (*Pachyta*) **E**: AL BH BU CR FR GE GR HU IT KZ MC MD ME RO SB SL SP ST ?SZ TR UK **A**: AB AR GG IN KZ SY TR

akbesianus Pic, 1898a: 6 ["Syrie, à Akbès"] - not available name

anticedivus Pic, 1914c: 14 (*Leptura*) ["Caucase: Arax; Brousse"]

anticonotatus Pic, 1914c: 13 (*Leptura*) ["Veluchi, Sarepta, Eibes"] - not available name

atroopicalis Pic, 1913b: 186 ["monts Amanus, en Syrie"] - not available name

eibesanus Pic, 1914c: 13 (*Leptura*) ["Syrie: Eibes"] - not available name

hungaricus Pic, 1913b: 186 (*Leptura*) ["Hongrie"]

italicus Pic, 1916b: 4 ["Lombardie"]

kalavritanus Pic, 1913b: 186 (*Leptura*) ["Morée"]

ragusai Pic, 1923d: 3 ["Sicile"] - not available name

rosinae Pic, 1901b: 11 (*Leptura*) ["Anatolie: Ak-Chehir"]

rufopicalis Pic, 1913b: 186 (*Leptura*) ["monts Amanus, en Syrie"] - not available name

rufonotatus Pic, 1913b: 186 (*Leptura*) ["monts Amanus, en Syrie"] - not available name

quinquepunctatus Pic, 1915g: 18 (*Leptura*) ["Südosteuropa u. Kleinasien" by Reitter, 1912]

septemsignatus Küster, 1848b: 89 (*Pachyta*) ["südlichen Türkei"]

siculus Pic, 1916b: 4 ["Sicile"] - not available name

subapicalis Pic, 1914c: 15 (*Leptura*) ["Akbès"] - not available name

testaceofasciatus Pic, 1913b: 186 (*Leptura*) ["Turquie et Syrie"] - not available name

unijunctus Pic, 1914c: 14 (*Leptura*) ["Syrie: Eibes"] - not available name

Fig. 1. *Brachyta interrogationis duodecimmaculata* (Fabricius, 1781): female, Southern Kazakhstan: Karatau Ridge, 10 km SE Karaoi vill., 43°13'58"N, 70°11'16"E, 700 m, 14.5.2025, O. Pak leg..

Figs 2-3. *Brachyta interrogationis miroshnikovi* Lazarev, 2011: 2. male, Russia, Karachay-Cherkessia, Daut, 10.7.1994; 3. Male, Russia, Dagestan, Buynaksk District, Verkhny Kazalin, 10.7.2004, V. Sofronov.

Fig. 4. *Stenurella (s.str.) melanura melanura* (Linnaeus, 1758): female, Russia, Bashkiria, South-Urals Natural Reserve, 22.7.2018, A.B. Ryvkin.

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4. An aberrant *Stenurella* (s.str.) *melanura melanura* (Linnaeus, 1758) female (Fig. 4) (Russia, Bashkiria, South-Urals Natural Reserve, 22.7.2018, A.B. Ryvkin) with prothorax unusually widened in the middle is preserved in the collection of V.E. Ustinov (Moscow, Russia).

5. *Trichoformafascius* Özdikmen, 2025a (type species *Callidium pallidum* Olivier, 1790) was proposed as a subgenus of *Trichoferus* Wollaston, 1854 for 2 species with peculiar elytral design - *T. pallidus* (Olivier, 1790) and *T. lunatus* (Szallies, 1994). But first, these species are not related, and second, such separation does not exhaust the diversity of the genus. So, at the moment *Trichoferus* Wollaston, 1854 = *Trichoformafascius* Özdikmen, 2025a, **syn. nov.**

6. All 3 new species described as *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 by Lin, Miroshnikov & He (2025) belong in fact to *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019 because of strongly swollen 3rd and 4th antennal joints in males, absence of lateral thoracic tubercles, relatively short 4th antennal joint, which is about equal in length to 3rd joint or just a little longer: *Bulbocerambyx gui* (Lin, Miroshnikov & He, 2025), **comb. n.**, *B. miaobenfui* (Lin, Miroshnikov & He, 2025), **comb. n.**, *B. liyuani* (Lin, Miroshnikov & He, 2025), **comb. n.**

7. According to Niisato (2007), populations of *Obrium cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767) are presumably represented in Russian Far East by Japanese subspecies *O. c. shimomurai* Takakuwa, 1984 (Hokkaido).

8. *Nathrius brevipennis* (Mulsant, 1839) was collected in Jordan (Aqaba gov., Wadi Rum, 989 m, 29°35'00.8"N. 35°24'57.7"E, [ex., *Ficus* sp., emerged 5.6.2024], 6.5.2024, R. Ambrus leg. is preserved in the collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

9. Özdikmen (2025b) proposed 4 unacceptable modifications: *Aglaophis* J. Thomson, 1857 was accepted by him as a genus name - in fact: *Anaglyptus* (*Aglaophis*).

He accepted *Aglaophis* (*Epodus* Chevrolat, 1863) and *Aglaophis* (*Metaglaophis* K. Ohbayashi, 1960); in fact: *Anaglyptus* (*Aglaophis* J. Thomson, 1857 = *Metaglaophis* K. Ohbayashi, 1960 =

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Epodus Chevrolat, 1863).

Akajimatora Kusama & Takakuwa, 1984 was accepted (Özdikmen, 2025b) as a genus: in fact: *Anaglyptus* (*Akajimatora*).

10. A male of *Clytus arietis* (Linnaeus, 1758) with the label: “Cyprus, Pafos, Coral Bay, 15.5.2016, S.I. Khvylya” is preserved in the collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

11. A female of *Clytus arietis* (Linnaeus, 1758) with 2 labels: 1) “Tunisia, Jendouba prov., Jebel Feidia Mts., 15 km NW Ghardimaou, 24.5.2007, Walter Grosser leg.”; 2) “ex larva, Quercus, 18.4.2008” is preserved in the collection W. Grosser (Opava, Czech Republic).

12. *Prominensipenna* Özdikmen, 2025c with type species *Trichorondonia kabateki* Viktora, 2024 was described as a subgenus of *Trichorondonia* Breuning, 1965. But *Trichorondonia hybolasioides* Breuning, 1965 - the type species of *Trichorondonia* Breuning, 1965 does not differ considerably from *T. kabateki* Viktora, 2024, so, *Pogonocherus* (*Trichorondonia* Breuning, 1965 = *Prominensipenna* Özdikmen, 2025c, **syn. nov.**).

13. *Agapanthia* (*Epoptes*) *dahli olegpaki* ssp. n. (Figs 5-6)

Type locality. Kazakhstan, N slope of Tarbagatai Mt., Maylyshat env., 47°47'20"N, 81°44'49"E.

The new subspecies is very close to *A. (E.) d. calculensis* Lazarev, 2013 which is distributed far northwards near Ust-Kamenogorsk (*Agapanthia dahli dahli* group of species). It is characterized by: relatively thin antenna, male antennae much longer than body, surpassing elytral apices with 6 joints, in females - with 4 joints; setae tuft of 3rd antennal joint well developed; 4th antennal joint with reduced setae tuft; black part of 3rd antennal joint very short, occupies about 1/5 of its length; elytral pubescence with hardly visible, scattered setae patches; humeral elytral area with same pubescence as dorsal elytral side; body length in male: 13.8 mm, width: 3.4 mm; body length in female: 14.3 mm, width: 3.6 mm.

Type material. Holotype (Fig. 5), male, Kazakhstan, N slope of

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Tarbagatai Mt., Maylyshat env., 47°47'20"N, 81°44'49"E, 10.6.2025, O. Pak leg. is preserved in the collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia); Paratype, 1 female (Fig. 6), with the same label is preserved in the collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to my close friend Oleg Pak (Donetsk-city), who collected the type series.

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Figs 5-6. *Agapanthia (Eoptes) dahli olegpaki* ssp. n.: 5. Holotype, male; 6. Paratype, female.

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